

Interaction of Carbons with Sodium Thiosulphate in Aqueous Solution

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Decomposition of sodium thiosulphate in carbon suspensions in water proceeds slowly in stoppered bottles and arises from and varies as surface acidity of carbons. The same reaction proceeds relatively faster in the presence of free supply of air in which carbon acts merely as a catalyst by virtue of the presence of unsaturated sites. Reaction under given conditions of experiment is facilitated more in the presence of carbon blacks than in the presence of charcoals. The use of sodium thiosulphate in any reaction involving carbons should be made with caution.

IN the study of interaction of iodine and carbon blacks, it has been suggested^{1,2} that the carbon, after the interaction, be titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution to estimate and distinguish between reversible and irreversible adsorption of the halogen. The tacit assumption made is that carbon as such has no interaction with sodium thiosulphate. However, in view of instability of the compound in acid medium³ and acidic nature of some of the adsorbent carbons⁴, it was thought of interest to take up the present work.

Experimental

Eleven samples of carbon blacks of varying degrees of surface acidity and surface area, besides two charcoals prepared by the carbonization of cane sugar and coconut shells⁵, were used as such as well as after outgassing at different temperatures so as to eliminate progressively the acidic oxide layer⁵. Portions were also treated with acidified potassium persulphate or aqueous hydrogen peroxide⁶ or nitric acid⁷ so as to build up more of the acidic oxide layer on the surface. Surface acidity was determined qualitatively by measuring pH value (using glass electrode) of aqueous suspension (0.1 g mixed in 10 ml of twice distilled water and shaken mechanically for 24 hr) and quantitatively by titrating against aqueous barium hydroxide⁵.

Carbon (0.5 g) was mixed with 50 ml of 0.2 N Na₂S₂O₃ in 125 ml pyrex-glass bottles and the suspension allowed to stand with occasional shaking in an incubator maintained at 25° (±0.1°) for a given interval of time. An aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was then titrated against standard iodine solution in the usual way. However, since bisulphite and sulphite ions, if any, formed during the reduction of thiosulphate ions, also react with iodine solution, a separate titration was also made on the addition of formalin⁸, in order to suppress this reaction. The second titre gave the actual fall in the concentration of thiosulphate ions while the difference between the

first and second titre gave the amount of bisulphate and sulphite ions formed during the interaction of the carbon with sodium thiosulphate solution.

In addition to the above experiments which were conducted in stoppered bottles, a few experiments were also made at the same temperature by bubbling air through the suspensions @ 3l/hr.

Results and Discussion

The amounts of sodium thiosulphate decomposed after different intervals of time in the presence of sugar charcoal, Carbolac and Spheron-C at 25° are presented in Table 1. The initial pH and barium hydroxide values of the carbons are mentioned at the top in each case. It is seen that the reaction proceeds fairly readily and to an appreciable extent in the presence of sugar charcoal and Carbolac which are highly acidic and to a relatively smaller extent in the presence of Spheron-C which is much less acidic. The reaction becomes very slow after about 16 hr in the presence of sugar charcoal as well as Carbolac and after about 8 hr in the presence of Spheron-C. The pH values of the suspension is seen to rise progressively and to approach or even exceed alkaline range in course of time. This shows that the surface H⁺ ions furnished by the carbons in replacement of Na⁺ ions (furnished by Na₂S₂O₃) are being consumed continuously in the process. The reaction appears to take the following course:

The HSO₃⁻ ion dissociates only slightly as its dissociation constant, being of the order of 10⁻⁷, is very small.

However, it tends to get slowly oxidised in the presence of air contained in the stoppered bottle.

[TABLE 1—DECOMPOSITION OF SODIUM THIOSULPHATE IN THE PRESENCE OF CARBONS AFTER DIFFERENT INTERVALS OF TIME

Time	Sugar charcoal			Carbolac			Spheron-C		
	Initial pH = 2.7 Surface acidity as measured by Barium hydroxide neutralization = 6.65 meq./g.			Initial pH = 2.8 Surface acidity as measured by Barium hydroxide neutralization = 2.84 meq./g.			Initial pH = 5.07 Surface acidity as measured by Barium hydroxide neutralization = 0.37 meq./g.		
	Amount of HSO ₃ ⁻ and SO ₃ ⁼⁼ formed (meq./g)	Total amount of Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ decom- posed (meq./g)	pH of the suspension	Amount of HSO ₃ ⁻ and SO ₃ ⁼⁼ formed (meq./g)	Total amount of Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ decom- posed (meq/g)	pH of the suspension	Amount of HSO ₃ ⁻ and SO ₃ ⁼⁼ formed (meq./g)	Total amount of Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ decom- posed (meq./g)	pH of the suspension
10 min.	0.25	0.25	3.20	Nil	0.35	4.20	Nil	0.17	5.08
20 min.	—	—	—	0.05	0.50	—	Nil	0.20	5.70
1 hr.	0.29	0.45	4.10	0.05	0.70	5.20	Nil	0.20	6.00
2 hrs.	0.30	0.60	4.90	0.06	0.75	5.25	Nil	0.22	—
4 hrs.	0.30	0.70	5.40	0.05	0.82	5.90	Nil	0.25	7.00
8 hrs.	0.30	0.85	5.85	0.05	0.85	7.90	Nil	0.30	7.75
16 hrs.	0.35	1.10	6.05	0.05	1.00	7.90	Nil	0.30	—
24 hrs.	0.35	1.20	6.25	0.05	1.10	7.95	Nil	0.30	8.05

The free sulphur formed in step (i) was found to get mixed up intimately with the carbon but could be recovered on refluxing with carbon disulphide.

It is also observed that only a part of surface acidity of a carbon has been used up in 24 hr time after which the reaction becomes extremely slow. Thus, in the case of sugar charcoal and Carbolac,

while the total acidities are 6.65 and 2.84 milliequivalents/g, respectively, the amounts of sodium thiosulphate decomposed are only 1.2 and 1.1 milliequivalents/g, respectively. The reason lies in the fact that beyond a certain pH, the replacement of surface H⁺ ions by Na⁺ ions becomes extremely slow and difficult⁹.

The amounts of sodium thiosulphate decomposed in the presence of different carbon blacks as well as sugar and coconut charcoals in 24 hr under the given experimental conditions are summed up in Table 2. The values for specific surface area, pH and surface acidity are also included in the table. It can be shown graphically that the extent of decomposition of sodium thiosulphate, in the presence of carbon blacks varies, generally, with surface acidity and not with surface area as most of the points would fit on a single straight line. The values for sugar and coconut charcoals, however, are seen to be much less than those expected from their acidities on the same basis. The reason probably lies in the porous nature of the charcoals. Some of the acidic sites located within the extremely minute capillary pores, accessible to OH⁻ ions, may not be readily available to S₂O₃⁼⁼ ions (thickness calculated from bond lengths, bond angles and Van der Waals radii being 6.4 Å)¹² for the reaction. In order to check this view, the experiments using Carbolac and sugar charcoal were also carried out at a higher temperature viz., 35°. It was found that while the extent of decomposition of sodium thiosulphate in the presence of Carbolac remained essentially the same as at 25°, the value in the presence of sugar charcoal increased from 1.20 to 1.45 meq/g, showing that S₂O₃⁼⁼ ions require activation energy to diffuse through the net work of minute capillary pores in charcoal.

TABLE 2—AMOUNTS OF SODIUM THIOSULPHATE DECOMPOSED IN THE PRESENCE OF VARIOUS CARBONS IN 24 HOURS

Carbon used	Nitrogen surface area (m ² /g.)	pH	Surface acidity as measured by Barium hydroxide neutralization (meq./g)	Amount of sodium thio-sulphate decomposed (meq./g)
Carbolac	839.0	2.80	2.84	1.10
Mogul-A	228.0	3.18	1.14	0.60
EIF-0	117.0	3.83	0.72	0.45
Spheron-C	253.7	5.07	0.37	0.30
Spheron-4	152.4	4.50	0.32	0.30
Spheron-6	120.0	4.59	0.32	0.20
Vulcan-Sc	193.0	7.22	0.21	0.20
Philblack-I	116.8	8.22	0.21	0.10
Philblack-O	79.6	8.82	0.16	0.10
Philblack-A.	42.8	8.50	0.10	0.05
Graphon	89.0	8.90	Nil	Nil
Sugar charcoal	412.0	2.70	6.65	1.20
Coconut shell charcoal.	—	—	3.58	0.70

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF OUTGASSING AND OTHER TREATMENTS OF CARBONS ON THE DECOMPOSITION OF SODIUM THIOSULPHATE IN 24 HOURS

Description of the sample	pH	Surface acidity as measured by Barium hydroxide neutralization (meq./g)	Amount of sodium thio-sulphate decomposed (meq./g)
<i>Carbolac</i>			
Original	2.80	2.84	1.10
Outgassed at 400°	4.00	1.80	0.60
Outgassed at 700°	6.00	Nil	0.25
Outgassed at 1000°	6.05	Nil	Nil
<i>Mogul-A</i>			
Original	3.18	1.14	0.60
Outgassed at 400°	4.30	0.59	0.40
Outgassed at 700°	6.10	Nil	0.20
Outgassed at 1000°	6.20	Nil	0.10
Original, treated with H ₂ O ₂	3.00	1.95	0.90
<i>Sphereon-C</i>			
Original	5.07	0.37	0.30
Outgassed at 400°	5.40	0.18	0.20
Outgassed at 700°	5.95	Nil	Nil
Outgassed at 1000°	6.40	Nil	Nil
Original, treated with K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	4.20	1.50	0.60
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>			
Original	2.70	6.65	1.20
Outgassed at 400°	4.00	3.00	0.50
Outgassed at 700°	7.95	Nil	0.15
Outgassed at 1000°	9.95	Nil	Nil
Graphon	8.90	Nil	Nil
Graphon treated with HNO ₃	—	0.19	0.18

In order to assess further the role of surface acidity of carbons on the course of the reaction, three of the carbon blacks as well as sugar charcoal were outgassed at increasing temperature so as to lower their acidity before using them for the reaction. The original carbons were also treated with acidified potassium persulphate or aqueous hydrogen peroxide to raise their surface acidity⁶. The results are given in Table 3. It is seen that as surface acidity falls on outgassing, the capacity of the carbons for the reaction falls considerably. On the contrary, as surface acidity increases on treatment with oxidising solutions, the capacity of the carbons for the reaction rises correspondingly. It is interesting to note that Graphon which, as such, could not cause decomposition of sodium thiosulphate at all (Table 2) can do so to an appreciable extent with the development of a small amount of acidity as a result of surface oxidation with concentrated nitric acid.

The results obtained under conditions of free supply of air in the case of some of the samples are recorded in Table 4. The values obtained earlier when the reaction mixtures were kept in stoppered bottles, using the same carbons, are also reproduced from Table 2 or Table 3, in a separate column for easy comparison. It is seen that the extent of the

reaction is now much more than before. This may, no doubt, be partly due to availability of more oxygen for step (iii) of the reaction. However, since some of the outgassed and other samples,

TABLE 4—AMOUNTS OF SODIUM THIOSULPHATE DECOMPOSED IN STOPPERED BOTTLES AND IN FREE SUPPLY OF AIR IN THE PRESENCE OF VARIOUS CARBONS IN 24 HOURS

Description of the sample	Amount of sodium thiosulphate decomposed in stoppered bottle (meq./g)	Amount of sodium thiosulphate decomposed in free supply of air (meq./g)	Surface unsaturation as measured by bromine fixation (meq./g)
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>			
Original	1.20	1.50	0.46
Outgassed at 700°	0.10	0.90	3.80
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	1.00	3.95
<i>Coconut shell charcoal</i>			
Original	0.70	1.00	0.38
Outgassed at 700°	0.10	0.70	2.90
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	0.80	2.95
<i>Carbolac</i>			
Original	1.10	2.30	0.96
Outgassed at 700°	0.25	3.05	1.68
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	3.10	1.88
<i>Sphereon-C</i>			
Original	0.30	1.10	0.70
Outgassed at 700°	0.10	1.30	1.05
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	1.30	1.10
Philblack-I	0.15	0.55	0.40
Vulcan-Sc	0.20	0.80	0.75

which were not at all acidic (e.g., Philblack-I and Vulcan-Sc), can also cause now considerable decomposition of sodium thiosulphate, it becomes evident that the origin of the reaction under the present conditions lies in some factor other than surface acidity. It was found in blank experiments that this reaction does not occur to any noticeable extent in the absence of carbons. It appears that carbons in the present case act as catalysts and that catalytic performance varies from carbon to carbon. The catalytic activity of carbons for various reactions has been shown^{10,11} to depend on the presence of certain unsaturated sites as measured by the amount of bromine fixed on treatment with aqueous bromine⁵. The bromine values of various carbons are recorded in the last column of the table. As can be seen, all the carbons are associated with such unsaturated sites. The outgassed sugar and coconut charcoals, having much higher bromine values can catalyse the reaction to a smaller extent than Carbolac. The reason lies again, probably in the porous nature of the charcoals. Some of the sites located within the extremely minute pores, though accessible to bromine (molecular dimension = 3.9 Å)¹², are not so readily available for reacting with thiosulphate ions.

It appears highly likely that this reaction is similar to that involving oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ ions in the catalytic presence of carbons¹¹. As was

shown there, the function of carbon catalysts, is to provide unsaturated sites where oxygen gets dissociatively chemisorbed. This, being an exothermic process, lowers the activation energy of the reaction

Thus the mechanism of the reaction involving decomposition of sodium thiosulphate in the presence of carbons varies with the conditions of the experiment, being different if the reaction is carried out in free supply of air from that carried out in stoppered bottles.

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